

Open Water IMTA

PRODUCTION MANUAL

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SUMMARY

This manual was created as part of the WP2 'New IMTA value chains and production methods' of the H2020 All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project. It provides detailed instructions of the cultivation techniques for each of the species trialled at the ASTRAL IMTA open water systems. The ASTRAL species included fed and extractive species of fish, seaweeds, molluscs, echinoderms and crustaceans.

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1. IMTA

IMTA is defined as the farming of aquaculture species from different trophic levels, and with complementary ecosystem functions in the same area or at the same site. This type of integrated culturing allows one species' uneaten feed, waste, and nutrients to be recaptured and converted into fertilizer and feed for the other aquaculture species. This approach takes advantage of synergistic interactions between species. The combination of fed aquaculture species (e.g., finfish or shrimp) with extractive aquaculture species, which utilizes the inorganic nutrients (e.g. seaweeds) and organic nutrients (e.g. suspension and deposit-feeders such as bivalves, urchins, sea cucumber) enhance growth in this type of system. IMTA systems can be open water or land-based, marine or freshwater, with a variety of different species at differing trophic levels. IMTA aims to aid ecological balanced systems to improve environmental sustainability, enhance ecosystem services, boost economic stability by increasing biomass, lowering costs, providing product diversification, reducing risk, and creating jobs in rural communities while advancing societal acceptability¹.

This manual contains detailed descriptions of the methods employed to produce the open water ASTRAL species trialled in this research project. This manual will give guidance on how to grow the species and the parameters needed for their successful production, including welfare, health and biosecurity. The ASTRAL open water species included fed and extractive species of fish, seaweeds, molluscs, and echinoderms.

¹ Chopin, T. (2013). Aquaculture, Integrated Multi-trophic (IMTA). In: Christou, P., Savin, R., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Misztal, I., Whitelaw, C.B.A. (eds) Sustainable Food Production. Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5797-8_173

2. SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON IMTA PRODUCTION AND IMTA RESEARCH PROJECTS

ASTRAL H2020 project

<https://www.astral-project.eu/>

IMPAQT H2020 project

<https://impaqtproject.eu/about-impaqt/>

IMPAQT massive open online course (MOOC) in Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and Precision Aquaculture

<https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/view.php?id=7116>

AquaVitae H2020 project

<https://aquavitaeproject.eu/>

AquaVitae MOOC - Sustainable Aquaculture for Low Trophic Species

<https://open.uit.no/courses/course-v1:UiT+SALTS101+AquaVitae/about>

INTEGRATE project (INTERREG Atlantic Area 2014-2020 Programme) – Transition towards IMTA in the Atlantic Area

<https://integrate-imta.eu/>

IDREEM EU FP7 project – Increasing Industrial Resource Efficiency in European Mariculture

<https://www.bmrs.ie/bmrs-projects/past/idreem>

The Benefits of IMTA

IMTA benefits are environmental sustainability through bio-mitigation, economic stability through product diversification and, risk reduction and social acceptability through better management practices. IMTA may lead to increased biomass production, waste reduction, and new opportunities with regard to spatial use and species diversification.

The following are the benefits IMTA can potentially bring to a predominantly monoculture activity:

- Reduction in ecological impacts.
- From a linear to a more circular model, allowing for a whole ecosystem approach.
- “Waste” reduction service to the industry through bioremediation. The “wastes” become “co-products”, using the vocabulary of circular economy.
- Additional crops produced in IMTA (e.g., seaweeds) can be used as feed or feed ingredients for fed species, enhancing circularity and reducing feed costs.
- Inclusion of seaweeds in IMTA allows for increased recirculation and a reduction in pumping (electrical) costs.
- Full recirculation in IMTA can provide protection to farms during harmful algal bloom (HAB) events (by not pumping seawater from the adjacent ocean during HAB events).
- Seaweeds in IMTA systems or as a feed/aquafeed ingredients have a beneficial impact on the microbiome.
- Improving the societal perception of aquaculture.
- IMTA grown products may have a market advantage.
- Different IMTA models can bring different community benefits – such as with the re-stocking initiatives.
- Optimization of the space available, numerous products to be produced within the same space, utilising the resource effectively and efficiently.

- Commercial benefit from growing other products in their site.
- Diversity provides alternative incomes and cash-flows, increasing the resilience of the business.
- Beyond biomass – true value in added ecosystem services and nutrient trading credits that some low trophic species provide before being valued at the farm gate².

² Chopin, T., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Troell, M., Hurd, C.L., Costello, M.J., Backman, S., Buschmann, A., Cuhel, R., Duarte, C.M., Gröndahl, F., Heasman, K., Haroun, R.J., Johansen, J., Jueterbock, A., Lench, M., Lindell, S., Pavia, H., Ricart, A.M., Sundell, K.S., and Yarish, C., 2024. Deep-ocean seaweed dumping for carbon sequestration: questionable, risky and not the best use of valuable biomass. *One Earth* 7(3): 359–364.

The Challenges of IMTA

The challenges faced by IMTA production are largely economic and regulatory. Generally, there is an imbalance in income between the trophic layers and this can discourage the adaptation of the concept. Adding other trophic levels to monoculture set-ups increases the complexity of farm husbandry and infrastructure, and increases costs and efforts. Farmers are familiar with current systems and change is unattractive and can be risky.

Further research needs to be carried out to demonstrate that profits can increase compared to those of conventional production systems. Issues of awareness and education about these innovative production systems need to be addressed. Concerns around biosecurity when additional species are introduced, or when water is recirculated or co-products are returned to the systems as feed, need to be researched and assurance given to allow for increased societal acceptance of IMTA products.

Competition for space when low-trophic, lower value, species are introduced into systems can cause problems; however, the economic, biological and societal benefits of integration need to be demonstrated. The whole value of the IMTA production systems and the ecosystem services they provide have to first be recognized. This is the phase we are presently in. Next will be the valuation/monetarization of these services and their uses for regulatory and financial incentives to make aquaculturists, regulators, aquaculture practices and society evolve.

Open Water IMTA

IMTA production can be carried out in several differing aquaculture systems. Open water IMTA, as carried out in the ASTRAL project in IMTA lab Ireland and IMTA lab Scotland, refers to species production at sea with mooring structures in place to anchor the growing structures to the seabed. This type of system is continuously exposed to the environmental conditions including wind and wave action. Figure 1 shows a potential IMTA set up in open-water.

Figure 1. Schematic of potential open-water IMTA scenario. ©Marine Institute

Temperate Climate

The open-water IMTA production described in this manual has taken place in temperate climatic conditions in Ireland and Scotland. Temperate climates are defined as having an average temperature above 0 °C but below 18 °C in their coldest month. Temperate maritime climates are characterised by the absence of extreme climatic conditions. This generally refers to mild winter temperatures and warm

summers. Rainfall is frequent but not extreme and the climate generally is free from hazardous atmospheric systems³.

Climate change effects often remain difficult to discern from natural variations in environmental conditions. However, marine aquaculture relies on coastal habitats known to be threatened by climate change impacts such as sea-level rise, warming coastal waters, changes in rainfall and storm patterns; to name a few. Expected impacts are strongly related to the industry's dependence on the marine environment for suitable biophysical conditions and may also create new niches and market opportunities for aquaculture species of the future⁴.

³ <http://thebritishgeographer.weebly.com/the-climate-of-the-british-isles.html>

⁴ Callaway, R., Shinn, A.P., Grenfell, S.E. et al. (2012). Review of climate change impacts on marine aquaculture in the UK and Ireland. *Aquat. Conserv. Mar. Freshw. Ecosyst.* 22, 389–421. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.2247>

1. OPEN WATER IMTA SYSTEM - IRELAND

Figure 2. Location of Irish IMTA lab Lehanagh Pool.

Lehanagh Pool Research site is a coastal aquaculture installation located 0.25 km from the shore in Bertraghboy Bay, on the West Coast of Ireland ($53^{\circ}24'03.3''N$, $9^{\circ}49'09.4''W$) (Figure 2). The site is a licensed 23.3-hectare multi-species research site. It is a fully experimental, non-commercial cultivation site operated by the Marine Institute. The site is within a sheltered enclosed area to the east of Bertraghboy Bay that is predominantly shallow (Figure 3). The location is relatively sheltered with no significant fetch or swell and waves are produced by local wind conditions. It is located approximately 1 km from the nearest pier used for site access. There are two sources of freshwater input, Cashel Bay and the Gowla River. The location of the site in the Connemara area of Ireland, is subjected to runoff from rainfall, reducing salinity and increasing turbidity with high particulate loading. Due to runoff, surface salinity ranges from 24 to 35 psu but is typically > 32 psu. Tidal range is approximately 5 m and water temperature ranges from 5 to 18 °C. The depth of the production site ranges from 15 m to 20 m. The mean current speeds are 0.040 and 0.028 m/s for mid-water and seabed, respectively, and residual currents and directions are 0.028 m/s at 171° and 0.015 m/s at 180° for mid-water and seabed, respectively. These low current flow rates indicate little dispersive capacity for fish cage waste. Any discharge from the cages at this site is likely to be dispersed initially to the south and any particulate wastes would be deposited to the seabed close to the cages. Infrastructure on site consists of a

traditional 5 x 50 m circumference pen grid for fish culture (Figure 3). This scaled down approach is approximately a quarter of the size of a commercial Irish salmon farm as the site operates for research purposes only. To the south-east of the pen grid, there is an attached Low Trophic Grid (LTG) consisting of a submerged rectangular grid with capacity for ca. 780 m suspended longlines (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Image of Lehanagh Pool research site looking north-east to south-west in direction of prevailing current. ©Marine Institute

Figure 4. Engineer drawings of low trophic grid, moored as an annex to the salmon pen grid.

The Lehanagh Pool mooring grid is made up of the following components:

- 14 x 500 kg Assembled HSS mooring anchors.
- Rope Danline 57 mm 3 strand.
- 10 tonnes of 38 mm open link chain.
- 12 x Warm galvanised mooring plates with 16 holes of minimum 37 mm diameter.
- 6 x 1100 L grid buoys.
- 6 x 1600 L grid buoys.

A 14-day simulation of the Marine Institute Bertraghboy model with particle tracking for upper, mid and bottom simulations was completed to assess nutrient dispersion sourced from fish waste at the pens. Based on the results of this model, the new infrastructure is orientated south-east of the pen grid (indicated in red in Figure 5). The location was chosen downstream of the modelled nutrient plume to maximize the potential for the uptake of nutrients from the fed species at the site. This new LTG is moored as an annex to the grid structure (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Heat map of particle tracking modelled of nutrients released from salmon pen indicated by the red dot. Black line indicates site boundary. ©Marine Institute

Figure 6. Surface image of low trophic grid on site fully stocked with all species. Colour floats used to indicate stocks. ©Marine Institute

The bespoke low trophic grid was designed to complement the current monoculture facilities to 'add' productivity (Figure 7). The grid model aims to maximize the use of available space and materials, while also minimizing environmental impacts. The design allows the operator to adjust orientation, depths, and spacing of culture lines using multiple attachment points to facilitate a range of low trophic species. As the grid structure is submerged there is less visual impact, suspended culture limits interaction with the benthic environment and by utilising the main grid for fish culture, the co-location maximises uptake of nutrients released from fish rearing activities and reduces the number of anchor points by 50 % when compared to traditional longlines.

Figure 7. Lehanagh Pool low trophic grid (LTG) adjacent to the salmon pens.

By creating this new structure there is increased habitat and biodiversity at the site for low trophic species, and a reduction in the environmental nutrient load, delivering a healthier production system.

This novel set-up maximises the use of space at this site and adds to the development of circularity within the production system. Careful consideration is given to the materials used to balance longevity of components, with appropriate end of life disposal such as recycling and renewables. The design also allows multiple uses for single pieces of infrastructure, future proofing, and planning for continued sustainable research at the site.

Table 1 contains the materials and components used to construct the LTG.

Table 1. Equipment and materials used to create and install the LTG.

EQUIPMENT DESCRIPTION	MATERIAL
Damper buoys 1100 L	Rotomolded PE and filled with Polystyrene foam. Density Foam 25kg/m ³ i.e. 580 L = 21.25 kg of Foam and remaining material is LLPE (51.755 kg)
Grid rings - round steel ring - masterlink 6" x 4"	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Ultraflex Aqua Plus 40 mm mooring rope with hard eyes 50 m	Polypropylene
Ultraflex polysteel 14 mm heel rope	Polysteel
OCEANFLEX unleaded 24 mm polypropylene riser rope	Polypropylene
Galvanised steel anchors	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Galvanised steel chain 19 mm 3 m	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Heavy duty galvanised steel chain 5 m	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Bow shackle 6.5 T	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Bow shackle 9.5 T	Heavy duty galvanised steel
32 mm grid rope with dyneema soft splice locks	Dyneema

A full catalogue of species trialled at the IMTA lab Ireland can be seen in the Table 2 below.

Table 2. Species cultivated at the Irish IMTA lab.

COMMON NAME	LATIN NAME	ROLE IN IMTA
Lumpfish	<i>Cyclopterus lumpus</i>	Fed species
Ballan wrasse	<i>Labrus bergylta</i>	Fed species
Atlantic salmon	<i>Salmo salar</i>	Fed species
Atlantic wakame	<i>Alaria esculenta</i>	Extractive Species
Sugar kelp	<i>Saccharina latissima</i>	Extractive Species
Black or Variegated scallop/Cluisín	<i>Mimachlamys varia</i>	Extractive Species
European lobster	<i>Homarus gammarus</i>	Novel species
King scallop	<i>Pecten maximus</i>	Extractive Species
Native oyster/ European flat oyster	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	Extractive Species
Purple sea urchin	<i>Paracentrotus lividus</i>	Extractive Species
Sea cucumber	<i>Holothuria forskali</i>	Extractive Species

The species at the IMTA lab Ireland (Figure 8) are categorized as: fed, extractive, benthic scavengers or novel species.

1. Fed species: Feed is inputted to the system for Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*) and Ballan wrasse (*Labrus bergylta*) when stocked. As a result, the fish release waste/nutrients into the surrounding water.

2. Extractive species: There are two types of extractive species. The filter feeders; Great scallop (*Pecten maximus*), Cluisin (*Mimchlamys varia*) and Native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*), filter out particulate waste (uneaten food and faeces) from the water as food, reusing the waste released from the fed species. Dissolved 'waste' is extracted by seaweeds *Saccharina latissima* and *Alaria esculenta* by absorbing dissolved minerals and carbon, reusing the 'waste' from the fish and shellfish entering the environment.

3. Benthic scavengers: Purple sea cucumber (*Holothuria forskali*) removes particulates from the upper surface of benthic sediments on the seafloor. This particulate 'waste' contains uneaten food and particulate waste from the fish.

4. Novel species: European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) utilise fish waste prevalent in the water column but also graze on the community structure established in the holding baskets. However, they are not grown to market size; instead, they are released as juveniles as a stock enhancement initiative linking coastal industries. Purple sea urchins (*Paracentrotus lividus*) are fed with the seaweeds grown in the IMTA process. They are incorporated into the food web by manual feeding, enhancing the circularity of this IMTA production system.

2. OPEN WATER IMTA SYSTEM - SCOTLAND

The IMTA lab Scotland, Port-a-Bhuiltin (PaB), is an open coastal aquaculture site located 200 m off the mainland shore in the Firth of Lorn-Loch Linnhe estuarine system, West coast of Scotland (56° 29.176 N, 5° 28.315 W) (Figure 8). The site has been operated as an experimental seaweed cultivation site by the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) since 2014.

The site is moderately exposed to south-westerly winds with the main current flow in NE-SW direction at average surface current speeds of 11 cm/s (range = 0.1 – 500 cm/s at 1.5 m depth). The tide is semi-diurnal (range = 0.15 – 4.51 m) with sea surface temperatures ranging from 6 – 15 °C and salinity from 24 – 34 psu (typically > 32 psu). The mean water depth is 30 m with muddy sand and mixed sediments beneath the farm.

Figure 8. Location of the IMTA lab Scotland Port-a-Bhuiltin (PaB), a low-trophic coastal aquaculture research site on the West coast of Scotland.

The site is licensed by Marine Scotland for the cultivation of seaweeds and, following an amendment in 2020, also for the integration of selected shellfish species for experimental non-commercial use. Thus, PaB has transitioned from a seaweed monoculture site to a low-trophic aquaculture (LTA) site for the integration of extractive species.

The total lease area is 30 hectares and currently consists of one tensioned 100 x 100 m (= 1 hectare) grid submerged 3 m below the surface. The grid can support up to 48 seaweed growing lines of 50 m length, spaced 4 m apart, which are suspended horizontally and parallel to the main current flow at a depth of 1.5 m below the water surface. The system is modifiable and offers capacity for additional deployment infrastructure for seaweed and shellfish production as well as environmental monitoring equipment (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Left: Site layout with seaweed and shellfish cultivation infrastructure and stationary monitoring equipment (selected). Right: Aerial view of the seaweed harvest operation (June 2020).

Cultivation species and production scales have focussed on European kelp species (*Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima*) and European flat oysters (*Ostrea edulis*). Under ASTRAL, additional LTA species are trialled (Table 3) including brown (*Laminaria digitata* and *Saccorhiza polyschides*) and red (*Palmaria palmata*) seaweeds as well as king scallops (*Pecten maximus*).

Table 3. Species cultivated at the IMTA lab Scotland.

COMMON NAME	LATIN NAME	ROLE IN IMTA
Atlantic wakame	<i>Alaria esculenta</i>	Inorganic extractive species
Sugar kelp	<i>Saccharina latissima</i>	Inorganic extractive species
King scallop	<i>Pecten maximus</i>	Organic extractive species
European flat oyster	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	Organic extractive species
Oarweed	<i>Laminaria digitata</i>	Inorganic extractive species
Furbelows	<i>Saccorhiza polyschides</i>	Inorganic extractive species

The species at the IMTA lab Scotland are categorized as inorganic and organic extractive species:

1. Inorganic extractive species: Seaweeds absorb dissolved inorganic nutrients from the surrounding water in their tissue. During photosynthesis, carbon dioxide dissolved in seawater is taken up by the seaweed and oxygen released as a co-product. Added oxygen and algal debris are beneficial to shellfish and other marine organism in proximity.

2. Organic extractive species: Shellfish are effective filter-feeders taking up dissolved and particulate organic matter suspended in the water column. They release nutrients back into the water column as part of their metabolic activity, thus adding to the nutrient pool available to other marine organisms, including seaweeds.

3. SPECIES PRODUCTION

3.1. FARM MANAGEMENT

All farm practices are subject to current legislation and license requirements. The management of an open water production site includes a number of checks that are carried out routinely and regularly on a site-wide basis; these observations are common to all the production species.

Routine Operations (daily/weekly)

- Surface visual inspection of the production site to include licensed structures, nets, moorings, navigation buoys and feeders.
- Recording of environmental parameters on site.
- Repair and maintenance of operational structures.
- Mortality removal as required.

Recordkeeping

- Stocking and feeding records to be updated as required.
- Record of environmental parameters.
- Record of health checks/visits carried out.
- Record the storage and use of chemicals and medicines.
- Site visitors log updated as required.

3.2. SEAWEED

(KELP: *ALARIA ESCULENTA*, *SACCHARINA LATISSIMA*, *LAMINARIA DIGITATA*, *SACCORHIZA POLYSCHIDES*)

In Europe, brown seaweeds or kelps can be found along most Atlantic coastlines, often forming dense forests. Kelp species are harvested from the wild and cultivated commercially, being a highly productive and fast-growing crop used mainly for food and feed products as well as for the extraction of high-value compounds (e.g. alginate and mannitol). On a global scale, Europe's contribution to seaweed production in general remains small compared to Asia, but interest and available market opportunities have expanded in recent years and will require the continued upscaling of local production to meet growing demands.

Seaweeds are on-grown from hatchery cultures which are seeded onto grow-out structures before being deployed at sea and left to grow until harvest; commonly 7 – 9 months from deployment to harvest, depending on the species and intended application (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Life cycle of seaweed species. ©Marine Institute & SAMS

Seed Supply & Transport

The seeding material, young seaweed sporophytes, can be sourced from designated hatcheries (e.g. commercial seaweed nursery operated by SAMS Enterprise). These offer various choices of cultured species, seeding substrate and equipment, and seeding strategy employed (direct and indirect seeding; the latter still dominating). Detailed rearing protocols have been established for the culture of main kelp species⁵ including biosecurity control to prevent contamination across species and with the environment. In general, best practice designates the culturing of endemic and locally sourced seaweeds and grow-out locally to its source.

⁵ <https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/BIM-Technical-Report.pdf>

Figure 11. Left: *Saccharina latissima* sporophyte culture; Middle: seeded twine reels in nursery tank cultivation ©SAMS. Right: *Kuralon twine* under x10 magnification with well-developed *Saccharina latissima* sporophytes ©Marine Institute.

For indirect seeding, better known as twine-seeding, up-scaled seaweed cultures are seeded onto reels holding fine polyester twine of 1 mm in diameter. The reels are then transferred into nursery cultivation tanks supplied with filtered UV-treated seawater and held under controlled temperature, light and nutrient conditions until juvenile sporophytes have developed sufficiently and evenly across the twine surface (Figure 11, nursery stage 4 – 6 weeks depending on species) and are ready to be transported for grow-out at sea.

Figure 12. Transport of seeded twine. © Marine Institute.

Reels should be kept moist and dark during transport using soaked clothes and a lidded box (polystyrene or cool box) (Figure 12). For longer journeys, ice packs and a temperature logger should be supplied to monitor temperature conditions during transport. Upon deployment, reels should be handled very carefully, avoiding touching of the twine and thus abrasion of the culture material.

Kelp Deployment

Site selection for cultivation is crucial. Physicochemical conditions must be suitable for the sessile kelp to grow and survive, being of adequate temperature, salinity, water movement (to deliver nutrients and carbon dioxide for growth) and light availability (low seawater turbidity to allow for light penetration and photosynthesis)⁶ (Table 4).

Table 4. Optimum environmental parameter range for kelp growth.

 Nutrients				
10 -15 °C	24-35psu	Low-moderate 0.1-1ms ⁻¹ (<i>S.latissima</i>) Moderate >1ms ⁻¹ (<i>A. esculenta</i> , <i>L. digitata</i> , <i>S. polyschides</i>)	50-250 ($\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) ¹	>10 (μM) ² Winter Nitrate (mmol N m ⁻³) Winter TOxN (mmol/m ³) ³

1. PAR (photosynthetically active radiation); photic depth being related to light intensity and thus optimum photosynthetic performance, affected by sunlight intensity and water transparency/turbidity
2. mostly nitrate (NO₃-);
3. total oxidised nitrogen (TOxN), nitrate and nitrite

For European kelp species, deployment generally occurs in the early Autumn. At this time of year, seawater temperatures and light levels are still sufficient for the young sporophytes to further develop their holdfasts and properly attach to the growing line before the onset of more severe weather conditions in later Autumn to early Winter. Surface seawater temperatures of ≤ 14 °C and salinities of ≥ 30 psu are recommended for kelp deployment. Optimal deployment conditions may vary slightly across kelp species; *Alaria esculenta* being more sensitive to sudden changes in salinity than *Saccharina latissimi*, but more resilient in strong current and wave regimes. Ideal deployment conditions include overcast weather, little to no wind, and no rain. Strong winds and direct sunlight can cause desiccation and physiological stress, affecting the condition of the fragile sporophytes and thus chances for growth and survival. Wind direction and tidal state should also be considered to allow for the work boat to drift downwind from the starting point (Figure 13). In general,

⁶ Kerrison, P.D., Stanley, M.S., Edwards, M.D., Black, K.D., Hughes, A.D., 2015. The cultivation of European kelp for bioenergy: Site and species selection. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 80, 229–242.

deployment should be performed carefully and efficiently, keeping environmental exposure and manual handling to a minimum.

Twine deployment can be performed manually or semi-automated (Figure 13) depending on the scale of the operation and equipment available, by applying the following procedure: (1) one end of the growing line (three-strand twisted high-tenacity polysteel 'seasteel') is passed through the reel; (2) the twine is untied from the reel on one end, unwound a few turns, and spliced into the growing line for secure attachment; (3) this start of the growing line is tied to a mooring point preferably at the far side (upwind) of the farm; (4) slowly and controlled, the boat is allowed to drift downwind whereby the seeded twine is wrapping helically around the growing line; (5) once completed, the end of the growing line is secured to the opposing mooring point. All personnel involved (skipper, person(s) handling line and twine) should communicate throughout the entire operation to ensure that tensions are maintained for the twine to deploy into the lay of the growing line and to avoid sagging.

Figure 13. Deployment at IMTA labs Ireland (top panel; ©Marine Institute) and Scotland (bottom panel; ©SAMS). Ireland: Manual deployment onto 28 mm growing line; Scotland: semi-automated onto 12 mm growing line using a seeding tool manufactured in-house.

Another important consideration is the spacing between growing lines. Environmental and practical considerations include allowing for an average swell in both directions to avoid line interaction and unobstructed navigation of the work boat. In addition, lines should be far enough apart to avoid shading effects whereby kelp fronds overlay one another which limits light exposure and photosynthetic capacity. Both open water IMTA labs commonly use line spacings of 4 – 5 m with narrower intervals and potential effects on seaweed yield and composition being trialled in ASTRAL.

Once seeded, growing lines should be tensioned and buoyed up according to the desired cultivation depth; for IMTA labs Ireland and Scotland this is approximately 1.5 m below the water surface. Buoyancy can be maintained using 8" trawl floats or polyform pencil buoys (e.g. LD20 buoys); the latter being preferred in medium-high current environments as less tensile force is acting on the growing line. A neutral colour should be used where possible to minimise the visual impact of the longlines as per licence conditions. Floats should be deployed approximately every 15 m along the growing line, using 6 mm Nylon cord cut to the required length (Figure 14). Since growing lines are positively buoyant and kelp biomass is not yet established, a 0.5 – 1 kg weight should be attached to each float connection to maintain the growing line at the required depth.

Figure 14. Deployment at IMTA lab Scotland, Oct 2023. Attachment of weighted polyform buoys along the seeded growing line. ©SAMS

Maintenance

As the seaweed grows, lines will rapidly become heavier and be pulled down. Therefore, line position, tension and depth should be checked regularly and adjusted as required by adding floats and tensioning up lines. Site visits for maintenance and monitoring (see below) should be performed at a minimum monthly as well as following storm events or extended periods of heavy weather. **Some common issues encountered, and their cause may include:**

- **Line drag or crossing** → heavy weather; recognized by altered float location and buoyancy.
- **Line abrasion** → floats/weights can wrap around the line and strip off on-growing biomass. Float connector ropes may be embedded in slim PVC tubes to increase rigidity.
- **Detached floats and/or mooring buoys** → heavy weather; require immediate attention.
- **Biofouling** → competition with crop for space, light and nutrients. Infrastructure should be cleared from heavy fouling and kelp harvested prior to onset of heavy fouling from May.

Stock Monitoring

Kelp grows comparatively slowly during the colder months but quickly enters their exponential growth phase in late February until late April, when biomass yields can double every 12 – 17 days, depending on the species (Figure 15). After this, growth slows down and yields stagnate or even decrease as older parts of the frond are shed and biofouling pressure (especially grazing organisms) increases (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Biofouling build-up after 3, 5 and 7 months (from left to right) at sea.
©SAMS & Marine Institute.

Depending on the site's operational scale and interests, stock growth and performance should be assessed regularly (monthly – bimonthly sampling) in addition to routine environmental monitoring for key physicochemical parameters such as temperature, salinity, and nutrient levels.

Kelp is sampled destructively for monitoring biomass yield, morphology/performance and biochemical composition (% moisture, ash, protein, carbohydrates, lipids). At sampling, the work boat is aligned and secured alongside a growing line. Using a tape measure a line area of 0.5 m is marked (Figure 16, left) and all on-growing biomass removed and placed carefully in a labelled net or bag and stored cool and dark for transport. This procedure can be repeated twice more along the line for a representative cover. Back on land and for each collected sample, the biomass is removed from the bag onto a clean work surface. For recording biomass yield, holdfasts are cut off and discarded and excess seawater removed from the biomass (= fronds with stipes) using a spinner; small salad spinner or industrial range depending on sample volume i.e. time of year. The spun-down biomass is weighed, and the value multiplied by a factor of two for biomass yields in kg per meter growing line [multiplication factor depends on the line area samples; e.g. factor of 5 if only 20 cm line are sampled]. If frond morphology is to be assessed, select 2 – 3 longest

individuals from the sample before spinning, lay them out flat and measure frond length and maximum width; after which these join the remaining biomass for spinning and recording of yield (Figure 16, middle and right).

Figure 16. Seaweed sampling and processing at IMTA lab Scotland. Left: *Alaria esculenta* sampling Jan 2021; middle & right: *Laminaria digitata* frond length and biomass yield in May 2021. ©SAMS.

Subsamples can be stored in labelled zip-lock bags and frozen at -20°C for analysis of biochemical composition or high value compounds of interest (e.g. mannitol or alginate). For analysis of trace metals such as cadmium, arsenic, iodine to name a few, required for seaweed entering the food and feed market, samples should be rinsed in deionised water before storage to remove excess salts.

Kelp Harvest

Kelp harvest is performed in Spring with the exact timing largely determined by the crops' quantity, quality and intended end use. Harvesting early in the season will yield lower quantities but ensures pristine fronds of high quality without biofouling damage; requirement when used for food and feed applications. A later harvest will yield much more biomass but of lower quality as damaged by fouling organisms and UV stress; for use as e.g. fertiliser rather than sold

as a food/feed product. Heavy fouling can also impact processing activities such as fermentation or anaerobic digestion used for e.g. biofuel production as calcareous fouling organisms may offset the pH buffering capacity.

Harvest types include (i) partial harvest: fronds are cut below the meristem in late Winter and left to re-grow for a second harvest in late Spring, and (ii) full harvest: the whole individual is removed either by pulling or scraping it off the line or by cutting the stipe. Harvest can be performed manually, semi-automated or fully automated using harvesting machines, and can take multiple days depending on the type of harvest and scale of the site's operation. IMTA labs Ireland and Scotland perform manual and semi-automated harvests, respectively (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Manual and semi-automated seaweed harvest. Left: *A. esculenta* line pulled into work boat and crop cut off by hand, ©Marine Institute. Right: *S. latissima* line is pulled mechanically (winch) through a shackle and the crop collected in tonne bags beneath. ©SAMS.

Ideal weather conditions are similar to deployment: little to no wind, no rain, no direct sun exposure (overcast ideal), and preferably low or outgoing tide to reduce pressure on the growing lines. Multiple work boats may be in operation to assist with the removal of lines, the storage in tonne bags or large fish bins, and efficient transport to land for further processing and/or hand-over to customers e.g. wholesaler, organic farmers, etc. Where possible, use a mechanical motor or winch to lift the growing lines out of the water – a 50 m line with e.g. 10 kg m⁻¹ biomass yield can easily weigh a tonne when wet.

The harvest season finishes with transporting all growing lines and ancillary material (floats, weights) to shore, where they are left to air-dry before power-washing and removing any remaining twine. Once clean and dry, growing lines are coiled and stored dry and dark for use in the following cultivation cycle (re-used for 2 – 3 cultivation cycles before reaching the end of life is). Any damaged ropes and floats should be cleaned and disposed of correctly in line with EU Directive⁷ on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment, also referred to as the Single Use Plastics Directive, and its relevance to aquaculture gear suppliers.

Sources of information

- A complete guide to seaweed hatchery and at sea grow-out design can be found at this link:
<https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/BIM-Technical-Report.pdf>
- A complete guide to the cultivation of *Laminaria digitata* can be found at the link below:
<https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/BIM-Aquaculture,Explained,Issue,26,-,Cultivating,Laminaria,digitata.pdf>

⁷ Directive (EU) 2019/904 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment.

3.3. OYSTER (*OSTREA EDULIS*)

The European flat oyster or native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) is a bivalve mollusc species found along the western European coast and the Mediterranean Basin, as well as North America, where it had been

intentionally introduced. Commercial production peaked in the 1960s and has since declined dramatically due to the impact of diseases (mainly Bonamiosis) and the consequential shift to the cultivation of more resilient Pacific cupped oysters (*Crassostrea gigas* or *Magallana gigas*). Production remained low throughout the decades with Spain, France, the United Kingdom and Ireland being the main producers. As availability decreased wholesale prices have increased, with *O. edulis* occupying an economic niche and being considered a luxury seafood item in many regions.

Seed Supply & Deployment

Seed oysters can be derived naturally (i.e. natural spat fall) using settlement substrates deployed at site. Where natural spat fall is sparse or unreliable, seed oysters should be sourced from disease free, reliable seed producers i.e. certified oyster hatchery. All regulatory requirements should be met in the procurement and transport of seed to the production site. The duration of the production cycle to harvest can vary depending on the size of oyster required by the markets (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Production cycle of *Ostrea edulis*. ©Marine Institute

In general, there is a wide variety of grow-out methods employed to cultivate oysters: on-bottom, off-bottom, longline and raft-based culture; often relying on natural spat settlement. This manual will focus on the method employed by both ASTRAL open water IMTA labs – floating oyster cultivation on longlines. The floating culture uses longlines deployed horizontally in the water column and serving as carrier ropes for shellfish baskets deployed in regular intervals. These baskets are equipped with their own flotation to maintain the system at the sea surface (Figure 19). The built-in flotation further makes the use of added buoyancy in the form of trawl floats or buoys redundant.

Figure 19. AP6 oyster baskets (3 holding baskets of 70 x 16 x 25 cm L x H x W [V = 72 l], mesh size: 2 cm²) deployed at both IMTA labs. ©SAMS

The oysters should be deployed within the nutrient stream from the fed species in adequate distance (approx. 2 m) (depending on the site’s location and hydrography). With the oysters being held in baskets, the operator should ensure suitable environmental conditions are met for growth and survival (Table 5).

Table 5. Optimal environmental conditions for *O. edulis* growth and survival⁸.

Temperature	Salinity	Dissolved Oxygen	Current speed	Chlorophyll
8-18°C	>30psu	>8 mg L ⁻¹	<0.5ms ⁻¹ Low-moderate	>8(µg L ⁻¹) ¹

1. representative for phytoplankton content thus food levels.

⁸ Laing, I., Walker, P., Areal, F., 2005. A feasibility study of native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) stock regeneration in the United Kingdom. CARD Project FC1016. Native Oyster Stock Regeneration – A Review of Biological, Technical and Economic Feasibility.

O. edulis is sensitive to overcrowding and thus care should be taken to not overstock the holding baskets. For IMTA labs Ireland and Scotland, baskets were stocked with 100 – 200 juvenile oysters (≤ 3 cm shell length) spread out over the individual compartments, respectively. Basket lids were additionally secured with cable ties either side to avoid stock loss during severe weather.

Maintenance

Oyster stock and infrastructure should be inspected regularly as well as immediately following storms and extended periods of harsh weather. Maintenance should be performed monthly and include the following actions:

1. Basket Damage: each basket and ancillary material such as connector ropes should be checked for their structural integrity and wear and tear. Damaged components should be replaced immediately to avoid stock damage or loss (Figure 20).

2. Fouling Control: the smooth basket surface attracts settlement of both soft- (filamentous algae; Figure) and hard-fouling organisms (barnacles, tubeworms, mussel spat, etc.). These compete with the oyster stock for food and space, obstruct the water flow through the mesh if not controlled, and can alter oyster growth and survival. Depending on the extent and type of fouling, baskets may be cleaned at site using wire brushes, or exchanged with clean baskets. Removed baskets are let to air-dry for the hard-fouling to dry out before being power-washed and re-used.

3. Grading: as the oysters grow more space is taken up in each holding basket. Oysters will grow at varying speeds, and small and large individuals should be separated to increase space and allow for even growth. For each basket, oysters are removed and roughly graded by size into batches of equal volume before being returned into the holding baskets. Grading should be carried out annually in the winter months to avoid unnecessary stress to the animals.

4. Mortality: during the grading process, any mortalities should be recorded and removed. These need to be disposed of following instructions given in the site's biosecurity management plan (BMP).

Figure 20. Oyster basket damage and biofouling cover. ©SAMS

Stock Monitoring

The oysters should be monitored continuously for shell growth and meat yield. Assessments should be carried out every 2 – 3 months or more or less frequently depending on the site’s scale and objectives. For this, 3 – 6 individuals are randomly chosen from each basket and transported cool and in the dark to shore. Either still on site or back on land, shell growth can be estimated by measuring shell height (SH) from the umbo to the highest part of the shell (Figure 21). For meat yield (MY), the oysters are opened and all soft-tissue separated from the shell pair. The soft-tissue is blotted dry, transferred into pre-weighed weighing boats and the total soft-tissue weight recorded. Shell pairs are also blotted dry and their weight recorded. Meat yield is an indicator for the ‘fatness’ of the oyster and is the percentage ratio of tissue to total weight (here tissue + shell weight to exclude trapped seawater; see Eq. below). The value can be corrected for size by dividing it by shell height (% MY/cm).

$$\text{Meat Yield (MY,\%)} = \frac{\text{tissue wet weight (g)}}{(\text{tissue wet weight (g)} + \text{shell wet weight (g)})} \times 100\%$$

Figure 21. *O. edulis* monitoring. Left: Shell height ©Marine Institute. Right: Tissue and shell weighing for assessment of meat yield ©SAMS.

Figure 22. *O. edulis* at IMTA labs Ireland (left) and Scotland (right). ©Marine Institute & SAMS

Shellfish Safety

In 2006 the European Parliament prescribed legislation pertaining to the quality standards for shellfish waters and requires that Member States designate the waters to which it will apply and set limit values corresponding to certain parameters⁹.

⁹ [Directive 2006/113/EC](#) (OJ L 376, p14, 27.12.2006)

Foodborne illness caused by microorganisms or naturally occurring toxins is the primary food safety risk associated with seafood¹⁰.

Seafood producers have a role to provide and carry out the necessary handling, processing, and inspection procedures to give consumers the safest seafood possible. Government agencies, retailers, processors, restaurants, and scientists also have commitments to ensure that seafood is safe for consumption. All requirements under appropriate legislation and best practice guidelines should be followed when harvesting and placing shellfish on the market (Figure 22).

Legislation and guidelines for aquaculture and aquaculture products in the EU, are categorised as follows¹¹:

- Requirements for production areas.
- Fish health rules.
- Labelling of aquaculture products.
- Hygiene rules.
- Microbiological criteria.
- Establishments subject to approval.
- Health Standards for Live Bivalve Molluscs.

¹⁰ Hicks DT. Seafood Safety and Quality: The Consumer's Role. Foods. 2016 Oct 28;5(4):71. doi: 10.3390/foods5040071. PMID: 28231165; PMCID: PMC5302431.

¹¹ <https://www.fsai.ie/enforcement-and-legislation/legislation/food-legislation/aquaculture-and-aquaculture-products>

3.4. SALMON (*SALMO SALAR*)

Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) is a well-established aquaculture species (Figure 23). Current worldwide production of farmed Atlantic salmon exceeds 3 million tonnes¹². There is a wealth of information available about the rearing procedures of this species, please see references below.

Figure 23. *Salmo salar* Atlantic salmon. ©Marine Institute

Production

The production of Atlantic salmon at Lehanagh Pool is in keeping with current open water commercial practices (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Production of Atlantic salmon at Lehanagh is carried out in line with commercial practices.

¹² <https://www.fao.org/3/cc0461en/cc0461en.pdf>

In an IMTA cultivation situation the rearing of salmon does not differ from that of monoculture methods or production cycle (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Life cycle of farmed Atlantic salmon. ©Marine Institute

The optimal environmental ranges for successful growth of Atlantic salmon are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Optimal environmental ranges for growth of Atlantic salmon at sea.¹³

Temperature	Salinity	Dissolved Oxygen	pH	Nutrients
12 - 15 °C	28 - 33psu	80 – 100 %Sat	6.0 - 8.5	Ammonia < 0.02 mg/L Nitrite < 0.1 mg/L

¹³ Marine Institute (2017) The farmed salmonid health handbook. Chapter III The Environment. IFA Aquaculture.

Sources of information

- The Farmed Salmonid Handbook – The Farmed Salmonid Handbook | Fish Health Unit
- Salmon Farming Industry Handbook 2023 <https://mowi.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/2023-Salmon-Farming-Industry-Handbook-2023.pdf>

3.5. CLEANER FISH – LUMPFISH (*CYCLOPTERUS LUMPUS*) & BALLAN WRASSE (*LABRUS BERGYLTA*)

Cleaner fish such as *Lumpfish Cyclopterus lumpus* (Figure 26) and Ballan wrasse *Labrus bergylta* (Figure 29) act as biological pest control on salmon farms as they help to combat sea lice infestations on the salmon stocks. The sea lice form part of the cleaner fish diet and have been successfully used on salmon production sites.

Lumpfish

Figure 26. *Cyclopterus lumpus* Lumpfish. ©Marine Institute

Sourcing of stock

Juveniles should be sourced from an appropriate supplier. The disease status of all incoming stock should be established by the producer in

order to adhere to the relevant legislation and fish health guidelines. The cleaner fish should be monitored continuously for welfare.

Assessing the effect the cleaner fish has on salmon livestock

Sea lice levels should be monitored frequently, with thorough sea lice counts in all pens.

Transport

At approximately 6–8 months old lumpfish reach a size of 25–40 g which is the appropriate size to be transferred to the marine salmon pens (Figure 26). Prior to movement the fish should be graded according to size. Fish are to be starved before transport for a minimum of 1–2 days. The transportation tank should be of suitable size for the number of fish being transported. It is important that this tank is dark inside. The tanks are fitted with oxygen supply and aerators. The fish are hand netted into the transportation tank. Oxygen is checked and adjusted (if necessary) every hour. It should be approximately 100 – 120 % saturation.

Lumpfish are transferred to the salmon pens by hand netting from the transport tanks. Special care must be taken not to forcefully remove lumpfish from a surface if they are stuck to it as this can cause severe damage, tanks are slowly tipped into the pen and held upside down. The lumpfish slowly drop from the surface they are attached to and fall into the pen. It is important that hides are deployed in the sea pen for the welfare of the lumpfish. A large temperature differential between the transport water and the ambient sea temperature should be avoided, efforts should be made to gradually adjust the temperature in the transportation tank to match that of the ambient temperature at sea.

Special conditions

The characteristic behaviour of lumpfish under stress (crowding or attaching itself to a surface by a suction disc on its belly) makes it difficult to distinguish unstressed fish from stressed fish, as the lumpfish do not display a typical flight response as is the case with salmon. Therefore, stress must be measured physiologically to expose the response. A lumpfish with 'calm' behaviour can be stressed.

Stress and any physical strain (loss of mucus and injuries) in connection with handling (loading and unloading from transport tank) are registered as significant stress factors for lumpfish, particularly with repeated handling in a short space of time, often in connection with secondary transport which requires transshipping of fish. Development of quick, gentler loading and unloading methods should take high priority.

Habitat enhancement

Lumpfish live the first part of their lives in a kelp forest and are to a large degree pelagic the first years before they leave the strand zone and migrate further out in the sea to search for grazing grounds. Lumpfish have no swim bladders, and in the kelp forest use their in-built suction cups to attach themselves on smooth surfaces, often in a hide in shade, probably for rest and as a natural protection mechanism. Plan for hides (Figure 28) to function as cleaning stations; a place where the salmon go to be relieved of sea lice. Good hides and adequate surface area are vital in reducing stress and ensuring good fish welfare. Kelp forests are serviceable for both large and small lumpfish, but the larger lumpfish (60 g+) often prefer settling on rigid surfaces. One way of creating shade is to have horizontal kelp ribbons the length of the curtained area on the water surface. Tail nipping and aggression may prove a challenge having sufficient hides will reduce this problem. Several types of hide are available on the market, such as ring hides, curtain hides and rigid hides.

Figure 27. Hides for lumpfish in-situ. ©Marine Institute

Placement of the hides

Hides must be positioned before lumpfish are released into the pen. Consider the direction of the sea current and feeding point for the salmon in relation to the placement of hides and monitor with the camera where lumpfish are most comfortable to make appropriate adjustments where necessary. Avoid placing hides alongside the net wall, by salmon feeding stations, resting close to the bottom of the net in a cone-shaped net or in the middle of the net.

Feed

Execute feeding in the refuge area and from separate feeding automats. Several types of automats are available on the market. Feed manufacturers (Biomar, Skretting, and EWOS) offer small pellets specially designed for lumpfish feed.

Recommended feeding rates:

After release into pen: 2 – 3 % daily feeding of biomass, daily up to 6 weeks.

Summer: 2 – 3 % daily feeding of biomass, 5 days per week.

Winter (<6 °C): 1.5 % daily feeding of biomass, 5 days per week.

Feeding in even doses during the day.

Some producers feed the lumpfish for 2 – 4 hours and finish the meal before the salmon have finished their feeding. It takes time to gather the lumpfish together, and the aim is to have the lumpfish ready in the refuges to go to work cleaning the salmon after the salmon have finished eating their meal.

If feeding is skipped for a day or two, the lumpfish will seek alternative food such as fouling growth, salmon feed or nip at sores and fins. It is recommended to hand feed a small amount during the workday to make observations/assessments of the lumpfish. Healthy fish will quickly react and capture the feed, and other fish that are sick or stressed will be slower to react.

Weight and length should be measured routinely to determine rate of growth and to calculate the right amount of feed to be given to the fish.

Welfare

Health inspections of lumpfish should be carried out routinely. The fish health service should be contacted if there is an increase in mortalities. Screening prior to transport and release is vital to reducing the potential for cleaner fish becoming a vector for disease. Common symptoms of disease or diminished health are emaciation, sores and wear-and-tear injuries to skin, cataracts or suction cup deformities. Erosion and tail rot are also common, in some instances also seen together with *Tenacibaculum sp.* and *Vibrio sp.* infections.

Ballan Wrasse

Figure 28. *Labrus bergylta* Ballan wrasse

Sourcing of stock

Juveniles should be sourced from an appropriate supplier. The disease status of all incoming stock should be established by the producer in order to adhere to the relevant legislation and fish health guidelines. The cleaner fish should be monitored continuously for welfare.

Assessing the effect the cleaner fish has on salmon livestock

Sea lice levels should be monitored frequently, with thorough sea lice counts in all pens.

Transportation

At approximately 2 – 3 years old Ballan wrasse reach a size of 50 g which is the appropriate size to be transferred to the marine the salmon pens (Figure 28). Prior to movement the fish should be graded according to size. Fish are to be starved before transportation for a minimum of 1–2 days. The fish are hand netted onto the transportation tank of appropriate size. It is important that this tank is dark inside. The tanks are fitted with oxygen supply and aerators. Oxygen is checked and adjusted (if necessary) every hour. It should be approximately 100 – 120 % saturation. Salinity of the water should never be lower than 25 psu, pH shall not be less than 7.0, and should preferably lie between 7.0 – 7.3. Upon arrival at the sea pens the tanks are slowly tipped into the pen. It is important that hides are deployed in the sea pen for the welfare of the Ballan wrasse. A large temperature differential between the transport water and the ambient sea temperature should be avoided, efforts should be made to gradually adjust the temperature in the transportation tank to match that of the ambient temperature at sea. Use a dip net for all handling. A kelp hide should be in place in the transport tank and in pen at the delivery.

Maintenance

Cleaning of nets, hides and other equipment is essential for successful wrasse biological control of sea lice. Plan and carry out routine cleaning of all equipment that is subject to fouling. If cleaning is sub-standard, the wrasse will prefer to eat the fouling instead of sea lice. Nets and hides should be washed at intervals of maximum 7 – 14 days in the worst periods for fouling. With use of wrasse over winter the hides must be cleaned before temperatures go below 6 – 8 °C. The hides should be cleaned regularly. Use of a mort collector can pose a problem regarding fish welfare. Wrasse often congregate in the dip net, and risk bursting when the net is pulled up to the surface. This is due (in contrast to the salmon) to the fact that wrasse have a closed swim bladder that equalises pressure through a gas gland, which takes a long time. With rapid upward movement from the depths, this escapes via the anus of the fish, and if the pressure is too great the fish bursts. **Measures to prevent swim bladder damage include:**

- Check via the camera if it is necessary to use a dead fish dip net.
- Avoid taking out dead fish the day after a large delivery of cleaner fish.

- Pull up the dip net slowly; maximum 20 cm/s.
- Jerk the rope to scare off the fish.
- Place hides so they reach all the way down to the dead fish dip net to lead wrasse away from the net. Use the camera to monitor movement.
- Ensure there are escape openings in the dead fish dip net.
- Pull the dead fish dip net up slowly all the way to the surface, so wrasse are able to swim out. If a stop occurs underway there is a risk that dead fish will float out from the net.
- Openings under the dead fish dip net may lead to escapes. These must be checked and repaired.

Feed

Wrasse must be fed consistently; it is recommended that feeding stations are provided in the hides. With wrasse feeds from Skretting (Clean Soft 12) and Biomar (Symbio Maintenance 12) (Figure 29), it is recommended that fish are fed from a submerged feeding unit. The feed is laid in a soft bait bag or a flexible nylon stocking. The bag must be made of soft material to prevent injury to fish noses. The bait bag/stocking is then placed in the hide, preferably at several feeding points at various depths. Bait bags/stockings should generally be refilled three times a week, less frequently when temperatures are below 6 – 7 °C. The need for refills can vary depending on appetite and number of bait bags in the cage.

Figure 29. Wrasse feeding block. ©Aquafeed.com

Welfare

Daily observations of the wrasse should take place. Routine health inspections should be carried out using recognised welfare indicators e.g. operculum damage, snout damage, upper jaw deformities, lower jaw deformities, emaciation, vertebral deformities, scale loss and fin damage¹⁴. The salmon is a natural predator of wrasse. To prevent this, the salmon should be fed before releasing the wrasse; the wrasse are particularly vulnerable immediately after release into the pen(s). Also having sufficient hides can prevent the problem.

Handling of wrasse before/during delousing:

Pay attention to the wrasse during delousing. The primary concern should be to keep the wrasse away from delousing equipment that is engaged in crowding, pumping and handling of fish. Some producers move hides to the opposite end of the pen from where the delousing equipment is located. Most of the wrasse stay in the hides, away from cast nets and weighted dragnets have passed under the hides. Nonetheless, watch out for wrasse that have become entangled in the cast net and end up in the well boat/delousing equipment. These must be retrieved and handled as gently as possible. Check equipment that is adapted to take care of cleaner fish during delousing operations functions correctly.

Habitat enhancement/Hides

Plan for hides to function as cleaning stations; a place where the salmon go to be relieved of lice. Several types of hides are available on the market, including ring hides, garland hides, curtain hides and Cunningham lanterns.

Curtain hides are often used as these offer the salmon plenty of opportunity to come into contact with the cleaner fish. The hide curtains are hung out in parallel lines where experience shows that a distance of 2 – 4 m between each curtain and 1 – 1.5 m between each kelp ribbon provides a spacious area where the salmon and cleaner fish can meet. The distance between the kelp ribbons must be

¹⁴ Kottmann, J. S., Berge, G. M., Kousoulaki, K., Østbye, T.-K. K., Ytteborg, E., Gjerde, B., & Lein, I. (2023). Welfare and performance of ballan wrasse (*Labrus bergylta*) reared at two different temperatures after a preparatory feeding trial with enhanced dietary eicosapentaenoic acid. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 103(5), 906–923. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfb.15482>

evaluated in terms of how many metres of hide one requires and how many hides are to be utilised in the cage. Producers have reported conditions were improved by increasing the number of kelp ribbons and reducing the distance between the kelp ribbons as one alternative to adding more hides.

Hides must be in position in the pen before the wrasse are released there. Ideally, hides should be placed so that the tops of the hides are 2–3 m below the surface in order to avoid the worst fouling zone. They are also located vertically in the water column to allow the wrasse the freedom to find a suitable depth according to seasonal changes in the seawater environment. Hides should be weighted at the bottom for stability. Place hides at some distance from the net wall to avoid having to move these before net cleaning. Plan for use of delivery hides with releases of wrasse, as these can act as a link to hides placed further out in the pen. Use of delivery pens can play a crucial role in acclimatising the wrasse to a new environment. This may contribute to reducing stress and facilitate wrasse establishing themselves in hides.

If faced with the challenge of cleaner fish seeking cover in the mort collector, you can steer them away from there by attaching a kelp 'climbing rope' (leader hide) from the mort collector up to the hides. This is done by attaching a weight on the middle of a long kelp ribbon and sinking this down to the mort collector.

3.6. LOBSTER (*HOMARUS GAMMARUS*)

The commercial culture of *Homarus gammarus* is difficult due to the slow growth rate, captive breeding challenges, low survival rates and cannibalistic tendencies (Figure 30). This crustacean species is included in the ASTRAL IMTA open water species production assessments not as a possible commercial aquaculture species but as a restocking candidate to potentially enhance the indigenous stock of lobsters for the local fishery. Juvenile lobsters are reared in a hatchery and grown to stage V or VI, and then transferred to sea for on-growing for a number of years before being released into the wild at suitable locations (Figure 31).

Figure 30. *Homarus gammarus* European lobster. ©Marine Institute

Figure 31. Production cycle of European lobster to adult. ©Marine Institute

The optimal environmental growth parameters are described in Table 7.

Table 7. Optimal environmental parameter range for lobster growth.¹⁵

 Depth			
5 – 18 °C	> 30 psu	> 90 %Sat	5 – 15 m

Sources of information

- A guide to hatchery rearing of lobster can be found at the link: https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/bimno_23_An_Illustrated_Hatchery_Guide_to_Producing_European_Clawed_Lobster_Homarus_Gammarus_2009.pdf
- This guide gives the procedures involved in the cultivation from hatchery to grow-out phase. <https://www.nina.no/archive/nina/PppBasePdf/rapport%5C2006%5C211.pdf>

Transport

All individuals should be transported separately to avoid any cannibalistic behaviour by each other (Figure 32). Transport in water from hatchery, monitor temperature of this transportation water and keep cool if necessary. Monitor oxygen levels, add aeration if required.

¹⁵ Daniels, C. L., Wills, B., Ruiz-Perez, M., Miles, E., Wilson, R. W., & Boothroyd, D. (2015). Development of sea-based container culture for rearing European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) around South West England. *Aquaculture*, 448, 186–195.

Figure 32. Transportation of juvenile lobster from hatchery to the sea site. ©Marine Institute

Deployment

Lobster are stocked into individual containers as part of a Sea Based Container Culture (SBCC) structure¹⁶ (Figure 33). SBCC units are suspended from longlines in the low trophic grid structure located in the nutrient plume from the fed species. Lobsters reared in SBCC structure are exposed to variable ambient biological, chemical and physical parameters which is likely to enhance behavioural enrichment for each lobster¹⁷.

¹⁶ Peter Halswell, Carly L. Daniels, Lars Johannig. Framework for evaluating external and internal parameters associated with Sea Based Container Culture (SBCC): Towards understanding rearing success in European lobsters (*Homarus gammarus*). *Aquacultural Engineering*. 83. 2018. 109–119. doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2018.09.005.

¹⁷ C.L. Daniels, B. Wills, M. Ruiz-Perez, E. Miles, R.W. Wilson, D. Boothroyd. Development of sea based container culture for rearing European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) around South West England. *Aquaculture*. 448, 2015, 186–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2015.05.026>

Figure 33. Deployment of SBCC lobster containers. ©Marine Institute

SBCC units are deployed at 3 culture depths, 5, 10 and 15 m. All containment structures should be identifiable (Figure 34), cable ties are used as a numbering system on each structure (Figure 35).

Figure 34. SBCC structures in-situ. ©Marine Institute

Figure 35. Recommended numbering system for individual lobster.

Feed

This species grazes independently on the fouling of its containment structure and also gathers nutrient from the wastes for the fed species on site ¹⁸. The SBCC allows enough detritus for sustenance as would be available in a rock crevice for a wild lobster.

Maintenance

All unnecessary fouling (Figure 36) should be routinely removed for the containment structures to prevent over burdening of the structure and the longline. Calcareous matter can be left as this is a good source of nutrients for the lobsters.

¹⁸ Baltadakis A, Casserly J, Falconer L, Sprague M, Telfer TC (2020) European lobsters utilise Atlantic salmon wastes in coastal integrated multi-trophic aquaculture systems. *Aquacult Environ Interact* 12:485–494.

Figure 36. Fouling of individual lobster container. ©Marine Institute

Growth Monitoring

Minimise time spent out of water by leaving remaining SBCC units submerged. Random sampling of individuals should be carried out quarterly to measure carapace length. Lobster growth is determined using gridded images and software to measure length.

- Remove the oyster stack from the water.
- Estimate and record the level of fouling (% cover biofouling of the lobster cages). Repeat for each stack. Include any additional observations such as variation in fouling intensity around the stack, alien species, species types.
- Starting from the top, note the number of cable ties to indicate stack number (1 cable tie = stack 1, 2 cable ties = stack 2, etc.).
- Beginning at the top layer, locate the triangular basket marked by a cable tie. This is the first in numerical order for this layer. Work clockwise around the container (Figure 35).
- Mark lobster as present/absent/deceased.
- Remove specimen and place in petri dish over gridded paper.
- Photograph specimen at 90°. Check photograph to ensure clarity, that an accurate carapace length can be obtained. (Figure 37).
- Place specimen back into compartment, replace lid and seal using elastic bands.
- Repeat with the remaining specimens.
- Reassemble stack.
- Reassemble stack. Return it to the water at specified depth.

Figure 37. Measurement of carapace length. ©Marine Institute

Predator Control

The SBCC structure provides protection from most predators. Regular observation and maintenance are required to ensure that all stacks are intact.

3.7. SCALLOP - KING SCALLOP (*PECTEN MAXIMUS*) AND BLACK SCALLOP OR VARIEGATED/CLUISÍN (*MIMACHLAMYS VARIA*)

KING SCALLOP (*PECTEN MAXIMUS*)

Scallop production includes both wild capture and commercial cultivation, with aquaculture contributing over four times more to the global total production (2.19 metric tonnes in 2017)¹⁹. Scallop culture is a relatively recent activity compared to other commercial bivalve molluscs (mussels, oysters, clams), originating in Japan in the 1930s in response to overexploited natural scallop beds, and since the 1980s being employed in many other parts of the world. European production is dominated by king scallop *Pecten maximus* (Figure 38)

¹⁹ FAO (2019) Global Aquaculture Production 1950–2017. Fishery Statistical Collection, Fisheries and Aquaculture Department.

and queen scallop *Aequipecten opercularis*, which often require > 3 years to reach commercial size (≥ 9 cm shell height for *P. maximus*) in European temperate waters. The production cycle will vary with the desired harvest weight (Figure 39).

Figure 38. *Pecten maximus*, King scallop, at IMTA labs Ireland and Scotland. ©Marine Institute &SAMS

Figure 39. Production cycle of *P. maximus*. ©Marine Institute

Seed Transport and Deployment

Scallop spat is to be transported in tanks with sufficient aeration and seawater at ambient temperature to avoid stress responses. Seawater salinity should be ≥ 25 psu and pH ≥ 7.0 , preferably between 7.0 – 7.3. As for oysters (see section 4.2.3), scallops are contained in grow-out structures thus environmental conditions at the cultivation site must be within the tolerance range of the species for growth and survival (Table 8).

Table 8. Optimal environmental conditions for *P. maximus* growth and survival²⁰.

 Chlorophyll				
10-17°C	30-35psu	$\leq 100\%Sat$	0.2 – 1 ms ⁻¹ Low-moderate	$>1(\mu\text{g L}^{-1})^1$

1. representative for phytoplankton content thus food levels.

Various grow-out structures exist for suspension culture with the most used being lantern nets but also stacked trays such as nestier trays, also known as SBCC (Figure 40). Suspension lines from which the grow-out structures are deployed should be submerged > 2 m below the water surface to minimise effects of wave action as well as sudden changes in salinity or temperature. Multiple suspension lines may be deployed in parallel whilst allowing for enough space between lines to avoid tangling of the suspension gear during severe weather events (often > 10 m spacing depending on the site's location i.e. exposure and configuration). The suspension line should be supported with floats deployed between rather than above grow-out structures to avoid abrupt tensile forces acting on the structures during storm events. The number of grow-out structures deployed from each suspension line can vary depending on the structure used, the vertical extension of structures (i.e. a 10-layered structure will be longer thus requires more clearance than a 5-layer structure), and the

²⁰ Laing, I., 2002. Scallop Cultivation in the UK: a guide to site selection. Lovestoft.

overall site's needs and capabilities. Grow-out structures should be deployed using an anchor or cloth hitch knot, ideally spliced through the suspension line, to avoid sliding.

Whilst lantern nets are negatively buoyant and as such do not require weighing down, adding a light weight can assist in keeping the grow-out structure in a vertical position and reducing lateral movement in moderate to high current environments. Stocking densities vary depending on the scallop size (being reduced with increasing age i.e. size) and grow-out structure and thus surface area in use. IMTA lab Ireland employed lantern nets with 10 – 15 individuals per layer whilst IMTA lab Scotland employed nestier trays with only 4 individuals per layer; worth noting that this was driven by the lower number of juveniles to start with which were also of larger size than the spat deployed at IMTA lab Ireland.

Figure 40. Scallops grow-out in lantern nets (left & middle) ©Marine Institute and nestier trays (right) ©SAMS.

Stock & Infrastructure Maintenance

Both the grow-out infrastructure and containing scallop stock should be visited regularly in line with the license requirements outlined by the respective authority such as the fish health inspectorate (FHI).

At open-water IMTA labs this was performed every 3 months and included the following actions:

- Cleaning or exchange of grow-out structures to remove on-growing biofouling limiting the water flow and thus food supply for the scallops. Removed structures should be transported to land, left to air-dry and power-washed to remove biofouling before being re-used.
- Stock count and removal and recording of any mortalities. Mortality disposal should follow guidelines set out in the site's BMP and excessive mortalities/stock loss reported to the Fish Health Manager.
- Scallop shells may be cleaned from on-growing hard- and soft-fouling (more relevant during the final grow-out to market size).

Growth Monitoring

Scallops should be monitored for growth throughout their cultivation period. This can be performed alongside the maintenance visits at 3-monthly intervals. Assessments may include the monitoring of shell growth (shell height and width; and total weight). Monitoring should be performed efficiently to minimise the time scallops spent out of the water.

Depending on the stocks' size a representative sample size should be selected. Shell height and width can be measured using calipers or a scaled length board. When following the growth in weight over time it is advised to clean off any shell fouling before recording total wet weight (Figure 41).

Figure 41. *P. maximus* morphological traits and recording at IMTA lab Ireland. ©Marine Institute

CLUISÍN (*MIMCHALMYS VARIA*)

This small scallop (Figure 42) is an indigenous species in the location of Lehanagh Pool. This species creates a natural spatfall and the collection of this spat has led to pilot investigations into the feasibility of this species as a potential aquaculture species.

Figure 42. *Cluisín Mimchalmys varia*. ©Marine Institute

Deployment

Figure 43. Deployment of Cluisín baskets. ©Marine Institute

1. Cluisín are stocked in Shellfish baskets (Figure 43).
2. Stocking density should not exceed 30 adult Cluisín per quarter.
3. Shellfish basket nets should be suspending from a submerged longline only and not a buoyant structure. If on a longline, do not position floats/ buoys directly above them.
4. Shellfish basket nets are positively buoyant and require a weight.
5. Cluisín should be submerged at a depth below 2m to avoid the influence of freshwater in Lehanagh Pool.
6. Shellfish basket units will be suspended from longlines in the low trophic grid structure onsite.
7. Shellfish basket nets should stacked with a maximum of 8 layers. A stop knot should be used to secure the structure. Fully close the layers using 4mm elastic and potting hooks.
8. All baskets should be checked for holes or damage to prevent stock loss.
9. Cluisín should be checked fortnightly for excess morbidity, stock health and signs of predator damage or after a severe weather event.
10. Any empty shells should be removed to prevent damage to livestock by laceration.
11. A full check of stock occurs every 3 months. This includes:
 - a. Shellfish basket nets should be cleaned by scrubbing the outside with a hard bristled brush. If fouling is excessive, transfer stock to a new clean basket.
 - b. Count total live individuals.
 - c. Cluisín can be cleaned, sponges, for example, should be removed.
 - d. A sub sample of minimum 20 is used for morphology and biomass, then frozen for contingent work. Cluisín growth is monitored by weight and by measuring the length and height of the shell using a length board following growth monitoring procedure.
 - e. Shellfish basket nets should be power-washed, cleaned, and stored indoors out of sunlight, if removed.

Feed

N/A as they are filter feeders.

Growth Monitoring

- Biomass accumulation – Quarterly measure and weigh n = 20 individuals.
- Record of morbidity must be kept.
- Minimise time spent out of water.
- Avoid full sampling on very cold days.

Equipment: Length board, data sheet, 250 g scales, camera, digital callipers, PE cord, clean shellfish basket.

Sampling frequency: Quarterly

- Record environmental conditions at location.
 - Using a boat hook – remove the shellfish basket from the water.
 - Estimate the level of fouling (estimate the % cover biofouling of the holding structure. Record on data sheet. Repeat for each structure. Include any additional observations such as variation in fouling intensity around the shellfish basket, alien species, species types.).
 - Check for signs of predator damage.
 - Clean outside of basket using a hard bristled brush. If fouling is excessive, remove all Cluisín and transfer to a new shellfish basket.
 - Whilst transferring stock, count total live individuals.
 - Remove and empty shells.
 - Where fouling is excessive, Cluisín can be cleaned, sponges, for example, should be removed.
 - Take a random sample of a minimum of 20 Cluisín used sampled for morphology and biomass, then frozen for contingent work (see sub sample method below).
 - Close Shellfish basket by threading the entrance using PE cord or twine.
 - Re-suspended from longlines using an anchor knot to avoid it sliding.
 - Remove fouled baskets to be power-washed, cleaned, and stored.
-
- Report excessive mortalities/stock loss to the Fish Health Manager.

- place Cluisín on length board and record shell length and height (see Figure 41).
- remove shell fouling (sponges, squirts, spat) and record Cluisín weight.
- remove sample from site and freeze to -20 °C for contingency/ further analysis.

3.8. SEA URCHIN (*PARACENTROTUS LIVIDUS*)

The gonads or roe of sea urchins are a highly sought after delicacy mainly in Asian markets²¹. The spiny sea urchin (*Paracentrotus lividus*) (Figure 44) is a candidate to help meet some of this market demand. The production cycle (Figure 45) may vary according to marketable sizes required.

Figure 44. *Paracentrotus lividus* purple sea urchin. ©Marine Institute

²¹ Stefánsson G., Krisinsson H., Ziemer N., Hannon C., James P. (2017). "Markets for sea urchins: a review of global supply and markets," in Matís report (Reykjavik: Skýrsluágríp Matís ohf – Icelandic Food and Biotech R&D).

Figure 45. Production cycle of farmed sea urchin²². ©Marine Institute

The optimal environmental growth parameters are described in Table 9.

Table 9. Optimum environmental parameter range for purple sea urchin growth²³.

 pH				
7 - 22 °C	> 30 psu	> 90 %Sat	0.2 – 1 ms-1 Low-moderate	Very tolerant >7

Transport

Sea urchins are to be transported in the hatchery water, temperature is to be monitored and not allowed to fluctuate during transport and kept cool if necessary. Oxygen levels are measured throughout transportation and aeration added, if necessary, saturation should not fall below 90 %.

²² Formery et al (2022). Developmental atlas of the indirect-developing sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus*: From fertilization to juvenile stages. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology* 10.

²³ Lawrence, J. M. (Ed.) (2013). *Sea urchins: biology and ecology*. Academic press.

Deployment

Figure 46. Urchin baskets. ©Marine Institute

1. Sea urchin are stocked in hexyl baskets (Figure 46).
2. Stocking density should not exceed 30 adult sea urchin per basket.
3. Shellfish basket nets should be suspended from a submerged longline only and not a buoyant structure. If positioned on a longline, do not attach floats/buoys directly above them.
4. Shellfish basket nets are positively buoyant and require a weight.
5. Sea urchin should be submerged at a depth below 2 m to avoid the influence of freshwater.
6. Shellfish basket units will be suspended from longlines in the low trophic grid structure onsite.
7. Shellfish baskets are secured closed using 4 mm elastic and potting hooks.
8. All baskets should be checked for holes or damage to prevent stock loss.
9. Sea urchin should be checked fortnightly for excess morbidity, stock health and signs of predator damage or after a severe weather event.

10. Any sea urchin displaying poor health or spinal loss where the teste is now visible should be considered moribund and removed.

11. A full check of stock occurs every 3 months. This includes:

- a. Shellfish basket should be cleaned by scrubbing the outside with a hard bristled brush. If fouling is excessive, transfer stock to a new clean basket.
- b. Count total live individuals.
- c. A sub sample (minimum 20) is taken for morphology and biomass, then frozen for contingent work.
- d. Shellfish basket nets should be power-washed, cleaned, and stored if removed.

Feed

Seaweed should be added to the shellfish baskets.

1. Sea urchin should be fed every two weeks.
2. Where diet is not specified, urchin should be given a mix of kelps. The quantity should be enough to fill the basket. This helps to cushion the urchin during periods of intense wave action.

Growth Monitoring

- Biomass accumulation – Quarterly measure and weigh n=20 individuals.
- Record of morbidity must be kept.
- Minimise time spent out of water.
- Avoid full sampling on very cold days.

Equipment: Length board, data sheet, 250 g scales, camera, digital callipers, PE cord, clean shellfish basket.

Sampling frequency: Quarterly

1. Secure boat alongside cage/ longline.
2. Record environmental conditions at location.
3. Using a boat hook – remove the shellfish basket from the water.
4. Estimate the level of fouling (Estimate the % cover biofouling of the holding structure. Record on data sheet. Repeat for each structure. Include any additional observations such as variation in fouling intensity around the shellfish basket, alien species, species types.).

5. Check for signs of predator damage.
6. Clean outside of basket using a hard bristled brush. If fouling is excessive, remove all sea urchin and transfer to a new shellfish basket.
7. Whilst transferring stock, count total live individuals.
8. Remove and empty shells.
9. Close shellfish basket by pressing down hard on the door clip until it clicks.
10. Further secure using 4mm elastic cord and potting hooks.
11. Re-suspended from longlines using an anchor knot to avoid it sliding.
12. Remove fouled baskets to be power-washed, cleaned, and stored.
13. Report excessive mortalities/stock loss to the Fish Health Manager.

Harvest

Sea urchin harvest usually occurs after 3 – 4 years of growth when the teste diameter is approximately 4 – 5 cm (Lawrence 2013)²⁴.

3.9. SEA CUCUMBER (*HOLOTHURIA FORSKALI*)

Sea cucumbers are a potential aquaculture species grown under aquaculture farms, not only as food, but as waste removers. The optimal environmental growth parameters are described in Table 10.

Table 10. Optimum environmental parameter range for sea cucumber growth.

Temperature	Salinity	Substrate	Current speed	Depth
5 - 15 °C	28 - 34 psu	Low mud	0.2 - 0.5 ms ⁻¹ Low-moderate	< 30 m

Transportation

Sea cucumber should be transported in seawater with aeration if necessary. The temperature of the transporting water should be equivalent to the temperature of the receiving body of water. The optimal environmental growth parameters are described in Table 10.

²⁴ Lawrence, J. M. (Ed.) (2013). Sea urchins: biology and ecology. Academic press.

Deployment

Sea cucumber cages are made from plastic coated galvanised mesh (10 mm x 10 mm), with a surface area of 1 m² and dimensions of 200L x 100W x 50H cm (Figure 47). The cages are anchored to the seabed on weights. Cages are stocked with either a high (six animals per cage) or low density (three animals per cage).

Figure 47. sea cucumber *H. forskali* feeding on sediment from inside holding cages. ©Marine Institute & INEVAL.

Growth Monitoring

Regular growth monitoring should be carried out to access the growth rate of the sea cucumbers. Individual animals should be gently dried of excess surface water and weighed routinely (Figure 48).

Figure 48. Weighing of sea cucumber. ©Marine Institute & INEVAL

Feed

Sea cucumbers form an active part in IMTA as they aid circularity by recycling nutrients, breaking down particulate and other organic matter from the benthos underneath the production site²⁵.

²⁵ Neofitou, N., Lolas, A., Ballios, I., Skordas, K., Tziantziou, L., Vafidis, D., 2019. Contribution of sea cucumber *Holothuria tubulosa* on organic load reduction from fish farming operation. *Aquaculture* 501, 97–103.

4. ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENTS

4.1. WATER QUALITY MONITORING

It is essential to monitor water quality parameters to ensure stock health. Regulatory requirements for the monitoring and reporting of water quality need to be continuously addressed. Optimal growth of all open-water IMTA species require good quality, well oxygenated water for optimal growth. Environmental parameters of interest and relevance and their recording frequency all depend on the operations scale, set-up, location, and species produced. For example, at sites holding fed species such as finfish, oxygen levels, water temperature, salinity and Secchi disk measurements should be recorded daily.

For many environmental parameters the site operator has the choice between manual water sampling and readily available off-the-shelf

sensors for autonomous real-time monitoring. Most physical parameters such as water temperature and salinity are easily followed deploying such sensors and are low in cost and maintenance. However, manual water sampling and subsequent analyses by an accredited laboratory are often preferred for nutrient levels. At the IMTA labs water samples are taken monthly and analysed for seawater nutrients important for seaweed growth (nitrate, nitrite, ammonia and orthophosphate) and phytoplankton content (estimated from chlorophyll-a measurements) in conjunction with analysis for amount of particulate organic carbon (POC) and nitrogen (PON) for shellfish species. In relation to the latter, phytoplankton sampling using a 10 m lund tube is conducted and samples are analysed in the laboratory for nuisance or harmful phytoplankton species. The biomass rating of the predominant species is also monitored on a bi-monthly basis.

5. HEALTH

Aquaculture establishments such as finfish farms and shellfish farms must operate in line with current aquatic animal health regulations. The EU Animal Health Regulation 2016/429 applies from April 21st, 2021. The Regulation lays down rules for the prevention and control of animal diseases which are transmissible to animals or humans.

EU Animal Health Regulations are as follows:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/429 on transmissible animal diseases and amending and repealing certain acts in the area of animal health ('Animal Health Law').
- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2018/1882 on the application of certain disease prevention and control rules to categories of listed diseases and establishing a list of species and groups of species posing a considerable risk for the spread of those listed diseases.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/2124 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2017/625 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards rules for official controls of consignments of animals and goods in transit, transshipment and onward transportation through the European Union.

- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/692 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards rules for entry into the European Union, and the movement and handling after entry of consignments of certain animals, germinal products and products of animal origin.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/990 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council, as regards animal health and certification requirements for movements within the European Union of aquatic animals and products of animal origin from aquatic animals.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/687 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and the Council, as regards rules for the prevention and control of certain listed diseases.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/689 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards rules for surveillance, eradication programmes, and disease-free status for certain listed and emerging diseases.
- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/690 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the listed diseases subject to Union surveillance programmes, the geographical scope of such programmes and the listed diseases for which the disease-free status of compartments may be established.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/691 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of Council as regards rules for aquaculture establishments and transporters of aquatic animals.
- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/260 approving national measures designed to limit the impact of certain diseases of aquatic animals in accordance with Article 226(3) of Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Commission Decision 2010/221/EU.
- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/620 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the approval of the disease-free and non-vaccination status of certain Member States or zones

or compartments thereof as regards certain listed diseases and the approval of eradication programmes for those listed diseases.

Marine finfish, shellfish and seaweed aquaculture in Scotland are licensable activities requiring a Marine Licence regulated by Marine Scotland – Licencing Operation Team (MS-LOT) on behalf of the Scottish Ministers. Additional entities such as NatureScot, the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA), the Maritime and Coastguard Agency, the Northern Lighthouse Board and the Public (managed through public consultation events) are all statutory consultees on Marine Licence applications.

As well as a licence to operate farm equipment, a Seabed Lease to develop or operate in an area within 12 nautical miles of the UK coastline must be secured from the Crown Estate (Crown Estate Scotland). Since 2007, all new finfish and shellfish farms in development require planning permission under the 'Town and Country Planning Act', issued by the relevant Planning Authority. In order to operate a fin-/shellfish business, authorisation for an Aquaculture Production Business (APB) and Aquatic Animal Holding Site Details must be submitted to and granted by Marine Scotland – Fish Health Inspectorate (MS – FHI).

All aquaculture products entering the human food chain must comply with Food Standards Scotland (FSS) to ensure food safety such as monitoring for toxins, pesticides, and environmental and process contaminants.

5.1. MOVEMENT OF STOCK

Fish health status must be considered when evaluating the risks of moving stock, both shellfish and finfish. Fish health regulations should be followed; these require that all transporters of aquaculture animals take specific measures to protect the health of fish during transportation, thereby preventing the spread of aquatic diseases. All equipment used to transport must be cleaned and disinfected after each use which safeguards the health of the species being moved. The process minimizes the risk factors that may predispose the species to disease, minimizes transfer of disease-causing agents and reduces the risk of accidental loss of stock during transport activities.

Species are checked to ensure that they are clinically healthy prior to movement. All legislative requirements should be met and permissions

sought, as required. A risk assessment should be conducted and the transfer of animals onto the site should only take place if the risk is acceptable.

All aquaculture production operations are legally bound to operate within their licence conditions regarding health of stock and biosecurity.

5.2. FEED AND NUTRITION

Only feeds that have been formulated specifically for the life-stage of the species being farmed are fed. Feeds and feeding rates are regularly reviewed. Organic feed should be used for organic IMTA production.

5.3. HANDLING OF STOCK

Handling is carried out with suitable equipment by competent personnel and during suitable environmental conditions. Environmental conditions are monitored as required (weather, water temperature, current, dissolved oxygen levels) to ensure optimum conditions. After a handling episode stocks are monitored for signs of poor handling such as injury. If such signs are noted, affected groups are carefully observed for increased rates of mortality or illness in the subsequent weeks. All handling events must be recorded in a daily log.

5.4. STOCKING DENSITY

Optimum stocking density varies according to the life stage, species, culture conditions and the environment. Stocking densities are monitored in relation to health, behaviour and water quality to ensure that welfare is not compromised.

5.5. PREDATOR CONTROL

Management methods are designed to reduce the attraction of predators to culture facilities and prevent predators attacking stocks thus avoiding stress that could result in an increased risk of disease.

5.6. MORTALITY MANAGEMENT

Mortality removal is carried out regularly to prevent re-infection occurring which could potentially compromise the health of the stocks and to prevent a deterioration of water quality. The frequency of mortality removal will be determined by the site manager based on time of year and numbers/type of mortalities. Records of mortalities must be maintained for each unit.

If a sudden mass mortality is experienced on a farm the following procedure should be implemented:

- The affected farm/site should be immediately designated as being in isolation.
- Where mortalities are due to infectious disease a zone of those units/sites deemed most at risk of exposure to infection should be established.
- Water quality should be analysed and all equipment regulating water supply and quality should be assessed for damage.
- If a notifiable disease is suspected the farm veterinarian and relevant authorities should be contacted immediately.
- Other farms within the 'at risk' zone should be notified of the diagnosis or suspected diagnosis.
- Non-essential deliveries or visits to the farm should be halted. Essential supplies should be delivered to the affected site last.
- Movement of equipment, vessels, personnel etc. between sites should be immediately halted. Movement of staff between the affected farm and other farms should be halted.
- Thorough disinfection of all equipment, clothing, vessels, etc. should take place if there is to be movement between affected and non-affected sites. Footbaths and, if practical, hand wash stations should be maintained and used by all personnel before accessing and leaving the site. These footbaths should be located at all access/exit points. They should be clearly visible and marked.
- Mortality removal frequency should be increased depending on the rate of mortality.

- Moribund stock should be slaughtered in a humane and rapid manner.
- Mortalities should be transported in sealed containers to avoid spread via spillage or predators.
- Stock should be transported to an approved disposal facility and rendered appropriately.
- Should slaughter of affected stock be necessary then strict disinfection and cleaning regimes should be adhered to. All blood-water should be contained and treated.
- An intensive sampling routine should be instated by the farm veterinarian and relevant authorities.
- All surfaces that come in contact with infected material should be thoroughly cleaned and disinfected.
- Unaffected stock should be placed under quarantine and monitored for a time period after the event, to be decided by the veterinarian, manager and relevant authorities.
- After the date of removal of the last affected stock from the facility an appropriate time period should elapse while the site remains fallow and before re-stocking takes place. Other sites in the 'at risk' zone should also follow this procedure.
- When restocked, the site should be monitored for a number of months for signs of disease.
- Additional measures may also be required in the event of an outbreak of a disease as listed in relevant legislative guidelines.
- Daily mortality records should be kept in relation to all affected pens. Records of all visitors to the site as well as details of all biosecurity measures put in place must be maintained and presented for inspection, on request.

5.7. RECORD KEEPING

Maintaining good records is essential to maintaining consistently healthy stock. Facilities must have an information management system

that provides timely information to identify and assess changes in stock health to allow for sound stock health management decisions. For individual groups of species in the facility, operators must keep up-to-date health records including disease history and patterns of mortality, and records of movements of stock within the facility.

With regard to fish stocks, accurate records of feeding rates (% body weight fed per day) and feed conversion rates (FCR = feed consumed divided by biomass increase) for each unit are particularly useful in tracking the health and performance of the stocks. Comparisons of feed rates and FCR between different batches of fish give vital clues as to the health of the population and the adequacy of the diet. Regular recording of growth performance and mortalities for each unit is essential for tracking trends over time and between sites. A weekly summary stock sheet should be produced. The stock sheet provides essential information for those who feed the fish but also for the site manager. This information is also required by the fish health professionals, regulators, insurers and for quality and customer audits.

The farm health records include:

- Inventory records – site name, pen/tank identification, stock type, number and biomass, pen/tank dimensions.
- Stock movement records – origin, strain, number, transporter details, mode of transport, dates.
- Mortality records including likely cause of death per farm unit.
- Daily stock observations.
- Veterinary reports.
- Vaccination records.
- Medicated feed records.
- Therapeutant treatment records.
- Records of mitigative actions (other than therapeutants) taken to prevent or reduce disease, e.g. taking stock off feed due to a plankton bloom.

- Results of disease surveillance, completed by a veterinary practitioner and by the competent authority.
- Disposal and movement of mortalities.
- Records of water quality parameters tested.
- Feeding records – feed type, feeding levels, FCR (Feed Conversion Rate).
- Biosecurity records – a Biosecurity Plan for the site as well as cleaning rotas, chemical logs, visitor records.
- Training records.

5.8. ADVERSE EVENTS

Severe weather conditions have the potential to generate 'emergency situations'. Staff are aware of the potential difficulties which may arise and are committed to mitigating any such problems. Structures and stock are assessed as soon as is safely possible after a storm event.

Structures are monitored routinely for fouling and are cleaned or replaced when required.

Extreme sea water temperatures should prompt the cessation of feeding and regular monitoring of dissolved oxygen.

Phytoplankton and jellyfish blooms can have a harmful effect on aquaculture. This occurrence should prompt the cessation of feeding and regular monitoring of dissolved oxygen.

6. BIOSECURITY

Best practice biosecurity should be carried out in all areas of the production facility. The implementation of an effective biosecurity management plan (BMP) is essential in reducing the risk of disease introduction to an aquaculture site. The BMP's objective is to ensure that the cultured stocks are reared in optimal husbandry conditions.

Biosecurity control measures should include:

- Introducing stock from disease-free providers and ensuring ongoing fish health and welfare.
- External barriers: Preventing the entry of pathogens.
- Internal barriers: Minimizing disease spread within a site.

External Barriers:

- Dips for footwear are positioned at the entry to the site.
- Ensure that transporters have carried out appropriate cleaning and disinfection procedures on vehicles, prior to entering a site.
- Visitor logbooks should be used with declarations of contact with other aquaculture stocks or wild stocks in the previous 72 hours.
- Ensure that there are adequate signs throughout the site informing visitors about biosecurity procedures.
- All regulatory requirements are followed.
- Predator control should be adequate for each site.

Internal Barriers:

- Each area should have its own equipment and where this is not possible; equipment should be thoroughly cleaned and disinfected when moved to another section.

- Clothing and equipment should be cleaned and disinfected before and after use.
- All disinfectants should be used according to the manufacturers' instructions.
- Logs of disinfectant replenishment should be kept.

Biosecurity audits should be carried out regularly to ensure that biosecurity standards are being continually met.

Table 11 sets out the requirements that should be followed to ensure the highest standard of onsite biosecurity.

Table 11. General Biosecurity Measures

MEASURES	FREQUENCY OF ACTION
A Visitors Book is maintained to record details of all visitors to the site and to ensure relevant cleaning and disinfection procedures have been followed.	As required in the event of external visitors.
Footbaths/disinfection points are available at all entrances to the site and records of disinfectant used and frequency of maintenance are maintained.	Checked daily.
Separate hand nets are retained for each unit within the site for removing mortalities. These nets are disinfected after use and nets are changed before they become heavily fouled.	As required.
Every effort is made not to share equipment with other sites. If this is necessary, the item of equipment is thoroughly cleaned and disinfected before it leaves the site and prior to it being returned to the site. It is disinfected again, on arrival back at the site.	As required, dependent on frequency of use
Specific Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), including wet gear are to be used for the site. Visitors must clean and disinfect their gear before they visit the site.	As required in the event of external visitors.

MEASURES	FREQUENCY OF ACTION
Containment structures are cleaned and disinfected at the end of a production cycle.	As required.
Workboats are regularly cleaned and disinfected.	Weekly
Where harvest bins and lids are brought onto the site, they are fully cleaned and disinfected beforehand.	As required.
Where harvesting occurs at sea or at the water's edge, all effluent should be fully contained and never discharged into the water column.	As required.
Screening/netting is maintained to exclude avian predators from containment structures.	Daily observations are conducted.
All equipment used in the retrieval of dead or moribund stock is cleaned and disinfected after use.	As required.
Mortalities are removed on a regular basis to ensure that on-site infection pressure is kept as low as possible. Mortalities are removed from the site and disposed of appropriately.	In line with farm management practices.

Sources of information

- **AQUAPLAN INFORMATION LEAFLET – Cleaning and Disinfection**

https://www.fishhealth.ie/FHU/sites/default/files/FHU_Files/Documents/CleaningandDisinfectionLeaflet.pdf

- **AQUAPLAN INFORMATION LEAFLET – General Biosecurity**

https://www.fishhealth.ie/FHU/sites/default/files/FHU_Files/Documents/BiosecurityLeaflet.pdf

7. WELFARE

All aspects of stock production should be carried out to always maintain high welfare standards and continual commitment is given to promote improvements as advances in knowledge and techniques allow.

The 'Five Freedoms', shown below, are supported throughout all stages of the rearing process.

- Freedom from hunger and thirst.
- Freedom from discomfort.
- Freedom from pain, injury or disease.
- Freedom to express normal behaviour.
- Freedom from fear and distress.

These freedoms are provided by:

- a) caring and responsible planning and management.
- b) skilled, knowledgeable and conscientious of stock husbandry staff.
- c) appropriate environmental design.
- d) considerate handling and transport.
- e) humane slaughter.

7.1. OPERATIONAL WELFARE INDICES (OWIs) FOR ATLANTIC SALMON *SALMO SALAR*

This protocol scores the welfare of individual fish based on a set of welfare indicators describing the appearance of the salmon. Each welfare indicator is divided into levels from good to bad. This OWI protocol can be used as an early warning system, alerting the farmer that something is potentially wrong with the salmon stock and warrants further investigation, preferably before mortality starts to increase. Mortality rate is the most used health related OWI. High or increased mortality rates indicate that there is a welfare problem on the farm. It is necessary to first confirm what is normal and then identify the causes of the observed mortality to take preventive actions. A low mortality rate does not necessarily mean that there is a welfare problem on a farm. Diseases and other issues may reduce welfare without causing

death. An OWI scheme devised by Noble et al. (2018)²⁶ suggests scoring 14 different indicators on a 0 – 3 scoring system: i) emaciation, ii) skin haemorrhages, iii) lesions/wounds, iv) scale loss, v) eye haemorrhages, vi) exophthalmia, vii) opercular damage, viii) snout damage, ix) vertebral deformities, x) upper jaw deformity, xi) lower jaw deformity, xii) sea lice infection, xiii) active fin damage, xiv) healed fin damage.

²⁶ <https://nofima.com/publication/1636395/>

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